

Strong reduction in near-surface turbulence due to aerosols in South and East Asia

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Abstract

Absorbing and scattering aerosols influence the vertical temperature profile and can lead to a shallower boundary layer and potentially enhanced surface air pollution. Using a regional chemistry-climate model, validated against >1,000 air quality monitoring stations, we show that absorbing black carbon (BC) aerosols reduce near-surface turbulence and boundary layer height through aerosol-radiation interactions (ARI). While ARI due to total aerosols lead to enhanced PM_{2.5} surface concentrations and 25,000-27,000 annual excess deaths in each of Northern India and Eastern China, ARI due to BC have a modest impact on near-surface PM_{2.5} because of its ability for self-lofting and enhanced precipitation affecting wet scavenging. However, over India BC ARI strongly increase the number of days with combined high temperature and relative humidity, dangerous for human health. These results highlight that the multitude of indirect impacts from individual aerosol species need to be considered to achieve efficient mitigation of air pollution.

Introduction

Large parts of South and East Asia suffer from poor air quality, mainly due to high concentrations of PM_{2.5} (fine particulate matter with a diameter <2.5 μm) leading to millions of excess deaths every year¹. Both through short-term and long-term exposure, PM_{2.5} can cause a number of detrimental effects on human health, such as respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, and other pollutants, such as ozone (O₃), add to the problem².

Local anthropogenic emissions are the most important factor influencing air quality in the highly polluted Eastern China and Indo-Gangetic plains of India, but meteorological conditions also play a key role³⁻⁵. Absorption and scattering of solar radiation by particles, i.e., aerosol-radiation interactions (ARI), have been found to enhance near-surface pollution by modifying meteorology in the planetary boundary layer (PBL)⁶⁻⁹, leading to an increased number of PM_{2.5} related deaths in China¹⁰ and India¹¹.

40 The enhancement of surface air pollution through ARI is a consequence of reduced
41 turbulence and lowering of the PBL height, leading to reduced sink of surface air pollution from
42 turbulent transport to higher altitudes¹². This is particularly important for black carbon (BC)
43 aerosols¹²⁻¹⁴, due to their ability to absorb solar radiation and thereby heat the atmosphere on a
44 short time scale¹⁵. BC in the PBL also leads to higher relative humidity, enhancing cloud development
45 and potentially affecting climate¹². Elevated relative humidity combined with high temperatures can
46 also have negative health impacts^{16,17}. The impact on PBL suppression is, however, dependent on the
47 vertical distribution of BC concentrations¹⁸⁻²⁰. Aerosols that scatter solar radiation, cool the surface
48 and therefore also modify the vertical temperature profile and stability, although the aerosol-PBL
49 feedback has been found to be small for sulfate (SO₄) aerosols⁹. In addition to ARI, aerosols can alter
50 the Earth's radiation budget through aerosol-cloud interactions where aerosols act as cloud
51 condensation nuclei²¹.

52 Aerosol-radiation interactions have been found to influence tropospheric ozone through two
53 mechanisms: meteorological changes by aerosol-radiation feedback, and changes in the photolysis
54 rates by aerosol-photolysis interactions²². The net effect is a reduction of near-surface ozone, mainly
55 due to aerosol-photolysis interactions²³, but the daily maximum ozone response is dependent on the
56 season²⁴. In addition to detrimental health effects, elevated near-surface ozone concentrations have
57 negative impacts on agricultural crop production²⁵.

58 Aerosol abundances over China have been reduced in recent years due to air quality
59 regulations while India has seen an increase²⁶⁻²⁹. However, regional trends in anthropogenic
60 emissions vary between individual aerosols and aerosol precursors³⁰, and there are uncertainties in
61 how natural emissions, such as dust aerosols, respond to climate change³¹. Thus, it is important to
62 gain knowledge on aerosol-PBL feedbacks due to individual aerosol pollutants. While BC has, in
63 previous studies, been emphasized as particularly important for triggering aerosol-PBL feedbacks
64 and exacerbating air pollution^{9,12,13,32}, there is a lack of knowledge on the quantification of its role
65 compared to other aerosols. Additionally, most previous studies have focused on relatively short
66 haze episodes^{12-14,32}, but in terms of health effects it is important to also investigate long-term
67 exposure of air pollution².

68 In this study, we investigate ARI (including adjustments) due to total aerosols and separately
69 ARI due to BC based on multi-year simulations, spanning the first two decades of this century, using
70 the Weather Research and Forecasting model with chemistry (WRF-Chem³³; see Methods). The
71 simulations cover a relatively large region in Asia, but we focus particularly on regions with large
72 anthropogenic aerosol emissions; Northern India and Eastern China. Additional single-year
73 simulations are performed to investigate ARI due to individual aerosol compounds. We focus on
74 aerosol-PBL feedbacks and resulting health impacts. Modelled near-surface concentrations of PM_{2.5}
75 and gas pollutants are evaluated against >1,000 air quality monitoring stations, and aerosol optical
76 depth (AOD) is evaluated against satellite observations.

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85 Results and Discussion

86 Model evaluation

87 The WRF-Chem model is able to reproduce satellite-retrieved annual and monthly mean AOD values
 88 over South and East Asia relatively well (Figure 1a-c). While the modelled values are generally lower
 89 than MODIS-Aqua in Northern India and, especially, in Eastern China, the model overestimates AOD
 90 over these regions when compared against the MISR satellite-retrieval (Supplementary Figure 1).
 91 This confirms that there are substantial uncertainties in AOD from individual satellite products³⁴. It
 92 should be noted, however, that the modeled AOD is based on diurnal means for all-sky conditions
 93 while the satellite-retrieved AOD are for a given overpass time and clear-sky conditions.

94 Comparisons of modelled annual mean near-surface PM_{2.5} against >1,000 air quality stations
 95 in China show generally good correspondence (Figure 1d-e). It is worth noting that despite extensive
 96 policies to improve air quality in China since 2013³⁵, near-surface PM_{2.5} in Eastern China was still high
 97 in 2019 (Figure 1d) (to put it in perspective, an air quality guideline of 5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ has been set by the
 98 World Health Organization³⁶). Probability density functions of hourly PM_{2.5} measurements are also
 99 well reproduced by WRF-Chem, especially for the year 2019, and a shift towards lower
 100 concentrations between 2015 and 2019 is seen in both the measurements and WRF-Chem (Figure
 101 1f). Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations are better reproduced by the model in countries that are
 102 outside of China but within the model domain (red dots in Figure 1e; Supplementary Figure 2).

103 Comparisons between measured and modelled near-surface gas concentrations (SO₂, CO,
 104 NO₂ and O₃) over China show more variable results (Supplementary Figures 2-3), but this can be
 105 expected given that the model grid spacing is 45 km while the measurements often take place in
 106 urban areas and are influenced by local emission sources³⁷. It should also be noted that the model
 107 has been run only with spectral nudging of horizontal winds outside of the boundary layer (see
 108 Methods), and therefore it cannot be expected that the model perfectly reproduces day-by-day
 109 historical conditions for such a large domain. Nevertheless, the model is able to reasonably well
 110 reproduce the seasonal and diurnal cycle of the gas-phase compounds, but with an underestimation
 111 for CO and NO₂, and too high nighttime concentrations of O₃ (Supplementary Figure 3). Modelled
 112 annual and monthly mean near-surface temperature and diurnal temperature range compares well
 113 against CRU observations (Supplementary Figure 4).

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115 Regional distribution of ARI

116 The modelled pattern of changes in near-surface turbulent kinetic energy due to total ARI largely
 117 reflects the distribution of near-surface PM_{2.5}, which has its highest values over India, Eastern China,
 118 and the Gobi and Taklamakan deserts in Central Asia (Figure 2a-b). ARI reduces turbulence in nearly
 119 the whole region, with substantial decreases of around 30% in Northern India, and exceeding 10%
 120 reductions in the rest of India and most of Eastern China. Changes in PBL height show a very similar
 121 pattern as changes in turbulence but with somewhat smaller magnitude, e.g., with around 20%
 122 reduction in PBL height over N. India (Figure 2c). The reduced turbulence and PBL height due to ARI
 123 imply that near-surface air pollution will be subject to less mixing and dilution. In fact, the model
 124 shows that near-surface PM_{2.5} concentrations are enhanced due to ARI by up to approx. 15% in
 125 regions that are already heavily polluted (Figure 2d). The desert areas are an exception, showing
 126 almost no change in PM_{2.5}, indicating that dust aerosols may be less efficient in enhancing air
 127 pollution through ARI. Also, ARI due to total aerosols change the mix of different PM_{2.5} aerosol
 128 pollutants, e.g., with dust aerosols mostly decreasing and carbonaceous aerosols (BC/OA), which are
 129 suspected of being more toxic than other aerosols^{1,38}, showing a relative increase that is larger than
 130 for total PM_{2.5} (Supplementary Figure 5). Nitrate aerosols increase due to ARI by 50% or more in
 131 large parts of India. The change due to ARI in the mix of different PM_{2.5} species is likely linked to their
 132 height distribution, for instance with nitrate particles mainly formed from agricultural ammonia
 133 (NH₃) emissions that are emitted at the surface level.

134 ARI due to BC also lead to widespread reductions in turbulence and PBL height, although
 135 with a smaller magnitude than due to ARI from all aerosols (Figure 2e-g). Interestingly, BC has been
 136 considered particularly efficient in enhancing air pollution through ARI^{9,13} but here it induces only
 137 modest changes in PM_{2.5} (Figure 2h). There are likely several factors explaining these different
 138 conclusions. For instance, Ding et al.¹³ also found strong influence of ARI due to BC on weakened
 139 turbulence and lowered PBL height using WRF-Chem, but the modelled influence on PM_{2.5}
 140 concentrations was only shown explicitly for ARI due to total aerosols, and not BC specifically; a
 141 direct comparison with our results is therefore difficult. In addition, their model study was limited to
 142 one winter month (December 2013) while our results are averaged over five years. In Stjern et al.⁹,
 143 different methods are likely to explain the different conclusions. They used a global climate model to
 144 simulate a tenfold increase in BC emissions, and were therefore unable to directly quantify the
 145 influence of ARI due to BC on PM_{2.5} concentrations. When averaged over the whole land region
 146 shown in Figure 2, the BC share of total ARI is 40% of the reduction in turbulent kinetic energy, 41%
 147 of the reduction in PBL height, but only 13% of the increase in PM_{2.5}. The two regions with strongest
 148 enhancement of PM_{2.5} due to total ARI, Northern India and Eastern China, are densely populated and
 149 with high near-surface BC concentrations (Figure 2d-e), and will be given particular emphasis in the
 150 further analysis to better understand the processes involved.
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152 Vertical distribution of ARI

153 Figure 3 shows that impacts of ARI due to BC are substantial in both Northern India and Eastern
 154 China, despite BC mass mixing ratios being small compared to other aerosol compounds. BC leads to
 155 strong atmospheric heating due to solar absorption (Figure 3b,j), up to around 0.5 K at 800 hPa over
 156 N. India and around half of that over E. China (Figure 3c,k). Aerosols other than BC are mainly
 157 scattering solar radiation and therefore cooling the surface, and both BC and non-BC ARI act to
 158 decrease the lapse rate and thereby strengthen lower atmospheric stability. This stabilization effect
 159 weakens turbulence (Figure 3f,n), and increases relative humidity near the surface (Figure 3d,l). A
 160 possible explanation for higher relative humidity near the surface in polluted conditions is that the
 161 decrease in turbulence leads to weakened transport of moist and polluted air out of the surface
 162 mixed layer and weakened transport of dry and clean air into the mixed layer from above¹². The
 163 modelled increase in cloud fraction throughout the atmospheric column for N. India, and the small
 164 change in cloud fraction for E. China (Figure 3e,m), agree with a former multi-model study of BC
 165 impacts (ref.³⁹, their Figure 7).

166 Over both regions, ARI lead to increases in PM_{2.5} in the PBL, with >5% near the surface, and
 167 decreases in the middle troposphere, but BC ARI alone shows the opposite effect: decrease in PM_{2.5}
 168 in the PBL (except near the surface) and increase above (Figure 3h,p). The self-lofting ability of BC
 169 has been shown to increase ascent over southern Asia⁴⁰, and this is indeed the case here as well
 170 (Figure 3g,o), largely explaining how BC ARI influence the PM_{2.5} vertical profile. In addition, the
 171 model shows that BC ARI increases precipitation in N. India, and partly also E. China, likely leading to
 172 stronger removal of aerosols through wet scavenging due to BC compared to the effect of ARI due to
 173 total aerosols (Supplementary Figure 6). Several studies have tried to isolate the role of BC to
 174 precipitation over India and China and results are somewhat contrasting. While some find that
 175 Indian BC emissions cause local drying⁴²⁻⁴⁴, other find insignificant precipitation change^{45,46}.
 176 However, monsoon season precipitation over India is found to increase in response to BC aerosols
 177 over China, or when perturbing BC globally or at least over both China and India simultaneously<sup>41-
 178 44,47</sup> – consistent with our findings. In the same studies, precipitation over China was found to
 179 decrease locally following an increase in BC, although comparisons to this study is more difficult due
 180 to larger differences in the East China domain.

181 Figure 3 also shows that ARI due to all individual aerosol types lead to increased PM_{2.5}
 182 concentrations in the PBL in the two regions, with organic aerosols being the largest contributor.
 183 Dust aerosols have a different vertical profile than other aerosols, with relatively large

184 concentrations in the middle troposphere in the two regions, likely because dust is transported into
 185 the region while other aerosols have more local sources. This leads to a strong stabilization effect
 186 and reduction of turbulence due to ARI from dust-only, and subsequent effects on the vertical
 187 profile of relative humidity and clouds.
 188

189 **Seasonal changes in ARI**

190 Figure 4 shows that the effects of ARI are unevenly distributed throughout the year for N. India, but
 191 less so for E. China. ARI from all aerosols lead to an increase in relative humidity and a decrease in
 192 turbulence throughout the year for both regions, and a large part is due to BC ARI (Figure 4e-f,i-j).
 193 Over N. India, the decreased turbulence and increased PM_{2.5} due to ARI from all aerosols are
 194 particularly strong in the post-monsoon (SON) and winter (DJF) season, when the concentrations of
 195 anthropogenic aerosols are high (Figure 4a,i,k). The PM_{2.5} enhancement reaches 25% in November
 196 and December 2015 with 7% contribution from BC ARI, and approximately the same contribution
 197 from ARI due to organic aerosols (Figure 4k). In the monsoon season (JJA), both ARI due to all
 198 aerosols and ARI due to BC lead to enhanced precipitation, and PM_{2.5} concentrations are reduced
 199 due to more wet scavenging (Figure 4g,k). Over E. China, the PM_{2.5} enhancement due to ARI from all
 200 aerosols is within 12% for 2015, and that due to ARI from BC is near-zero, throughout the year
 201 (Figure 4l). In both regions, most effects of ARI are fairly constant between the simulated years
 202 (ranging from 2003 to 2019), except that PM_{2.5} enhancements over N. India have increased since the
 203 beginning of the time period (Supplementary Figure 7).
 204

205 **Impacts of ARI on health-related metrics**

206 Figure 5a shows that the change in near-surface concentrations of PM_{2.5} due to ARI from all aerosols
 207 leads to excess mortality in several regions, with total changes in annual excess deaths due to PM_{2.5}
 208 of +27,200, +24,900, and +76,900 in N. India, E. China, and the whole domain, respectively.
 209 Corresponding numbers for ARI due to BC are +1,930, +426, and -8,190, respectively, and the
 210 distribution is shown in Figure 5e. For comparison, the estimated number of annual excess deaths
 211 due to PM_{2.5} in the BASE simulation is 0.613 [0.478-0.792; 95% CI], 0.665 [0.531-0.834], and 2.74
 212 [2.11-3.59] million in N. India, E. China, and the whole domain, respectively (Supplementary Figure
 213 8). This means that ARI constitute 4% of the annual excess deaths due to PM_{2.5} in each of the two
 214 regions, and 3% when aggregated over the whole domain. While ARI due to all aerosols affect excess
 215 deaths of elderly people the most in the domain as a whole, a relatively large share (31%) of excess
 216 deaths in N. India are among middle adulthood and younger populations (age <60 years)
 217 (Supplementary Figure 9), partly due to a younger population. In this region, excess mortality due to
 218 ARI from BC has increased substantially in the later years (2015 and 2019). In both N. India and E.
 219 China, ARI due to all aerosols, and especially due to BC, lead to a particularly large increase in deaths
 220 due to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. It is worth noting that while excess deaths of adults in
 221 the domain as a whole are reduced due to ARI from BC, the BC still leads to an increase in excess
 222 deaths caused by lower respiratory infection among children.

223 The above health impact calculations are based on annual concentrations of PM_{2.5}, but short-
 224 term exposure of elevated air pollution are also associated with a number of detrimental health
 225 effects². Results show that the number of haze days, defined here as PM_{2.5} daily mean concentration
 226 higher than the WHO interim target 1 of 75 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ ³⁶, increases by more than 30 days in large parts
 227 of N. India due to ARI from all aerosols, with smaller but non-negligible contribution from BC ARI
 228 (Figure 5b,f).

229 The effect of ARI on near-surface ozone is to reduce the concentrations throughout the domain,
 230 and BC is the main cause (Figure 5c,g). The amount of solar radiation reaching the surface is reduced
 231 by >5% in large parts of India and E. China due to ARI from BC (Supplementary Figure 10), and this
 232 would reduce ozone formation due to photolysis attenuation. However, dynamical changes could

233 also influence ozone levels²⁴, including the impact of relative humidity changes on ozone dry
 234 deposition⁴⁸.

235 Heat index, or apparent temperature, is a measure of the temperature felt by the human body
 236 when accounting for relative humidity⁴⁹. A heat index >41°C is categorized as dangerous and involves
 237 risk of sunstroke and heatstroke⁵⁰. Results show that ARI from BC substantially increase the number
 238 of days with maximum heat index exceeding 41°C throughout India and part of E. China, with more
 239 than 10 days increase in parts of N. India (Figure 5h). This occurs because BC enhances both surface
 240 temperature and relative humidity (Figure 4c,e; Supplementary Figure 11). In contrast, ARI from
 241 total aerosols cool the surface and show only small influences on the number of days with maximum
 242 heat index exceeding 41°C (Figure 5d), implying that scattering aerosols reduce this number of days
 243 considerably. For heat indices with lower thresholds, the number of days with exceedance is
 244 reduced due to ARI from total aerosols but increased considerably when analyzing ARI due to BC
 245 (Supplementary Figure 12).

246 Diurnal temperature range is the difference between the daily maximum and minimum
 247 temperature, and its variation could influence crop yields⁵¹ and human health, mostly with greater
 248 diurnal temperature range being associated with increased mortality⁵². Results show that ARI from
 249 all aerosols reduce the diurnal temperature range by 0.5-1°C in nearly all of India, largely due to a
 250 decrease in daily maximum temperature caused by scattering aerosols (Supplementary Figure 13).
 251 ARI due to BC lead to an increase in daily maximum temperature in most of India, and an even
 252 stronger increase in daily minimum temperature. Some studies indicate that enhanced night-time
 253 temperatures are of particular concern regarding mortality and morbidity risk, including humid-hot
 254 nights^{53,54}.

255 In conclusion, our results highlight the multitude of impacts from individual aerosol species on
 256 meteorology and air pollution. Most notably, BC is particularly efficient in reducing near-surface
 257 turbulence through aerosol-radiation interactions but, in contrast to ARI from non-BC aerosols,
 258 reduces the number of excess deaths caused by long-term PM_{2.5} exposure in southern and eastern
 259 Asia as a whole. At the same time, ARI from BC lead to increases in both near-surface temperature
 260 and relative humidity over India, in contrast to non-BC aerosols that cool the surface. Consequently,
 261 if potential future air pollution mitigation over India would involve reductions of scattering aerosols
 262 without simultaneous reductions in black carbon, as has partly been the case in China (ref.³⁰, their
 263 Figure 8), this could cause a substantial increase in the number of days exceeding heat index levels
 264 that are dangerous to human health.

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269 **Methods**

270 **Air pollution monitoring data**

271 China's air pollution monitoring data was from the national monitoring sites
 272 (<https://quotsoft.net/air/>). Air pollution measurements of annual mean PM_{2.5} and NO₂ in countries
 273 other than China have been taken from the WHO database v6.1⁵⁵.
 274

275 **Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) satellite observations**

276 Satellite observations of AOD at 550 nm (level 3) have been taken from the Moderate Resolution
 277 Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) instrument on board the Aqua (dataset MYD08_M3) and Terra
 278 (dataset MOD08_M3) platforms⁵⁶, and the Multi-Angle Imaging Spectroradiometer (MISR)
 279 instrument on board the Terra platform (dataset MIL3MAEN_004)⁵⁷.
 280

281 **Surface temperature observations**

282 Monthly-mean observations of surface temperature and diurnal temperature range have been taken
283 from the Climatic Research Unit gridded Time Series (CRU TS) version 4.08⁵⁸.

285 **WRF-Chem model simulations**

286 The WRF-Chem model³³ version 3.9.1.1 has been used at a horizontal resolution of 45 km x 45 km
287 covering a large part of Asia. The extent of the model domain is shown in Figure 1a, except that an
288 outer boundary of 10 grid boxes have been removed in the analysis to avoid spurious boundary
289 effects. In the vertical, 50 layers were used, extending from the surface and up to 50 hPa.
290 Meteorological initial and 6-hourly boundary conditions, including sea-surface temperatures, were
291 taken from the ERA5 reanalysis data⁵⁹. Spectral nudging of horizontal winds were applied outside of
292 the PBL. Physics schemes applied include the RRTMG radiation scheme⁶⁰, Morrison 2-moment
293 microphysics scheme⁶¹, MYNN PBL and surface layer scheme⁶², Unified Noah land surface model⁶³,
294 and Grell 3D ensemble cumulus parameterization scheme⁶⁴. Although the WRF-Chem model version
295 is 3.9.1.1, relevant bug fixes have been applied up until version 4.4. The cloud fraction diagnosis was
296 modified to follow Xu and Randall⁶⁵.

297 Gas-phase chemistry is represented by the MOZART mechanism⁶⁶ and aerosols by the
298 MOSAIC 4-bin sectional aerosol module⁶⁷ including aqueous chemistry and aerosol-cloud
299 interactions. Chemical initial and boundary conditions are from CESM2.1/CAM-Chem^{68,69}.
300 Anthropogenic emissions are from the Community Emissions Data System (CEDS) version of April
301 2021, which goes until 2019 and builds upon the CEDS system described in ref.³⁰. Sector-dependent
302 factors have been applied to crudely account for vertical distribution⁷⁰ and temporal (weekly and
303 diurnal variations) profiles⁷¹. Biomass burning emissions are from the CMIP6 inventory, which goes
304 until 2015⁷², and 2015 emissions are assumed also for 2019. The biomass burning emissions have
305 been distributed evenly between the surface and 1.2 km height in the vertical, and a diurnal cycle
306 has been assumed as in ref.⁷³ (their Table 9). The calculation of biogenic emissions is done online
307 using the Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from Nature (MEGAN) version 2.04⁷⁴. Natural
308 dust and sea salt emissions are also calculated online, while dimethyl sulfide (DMS) emissions use
309 the sea-air exchange fluxes of ref.⁷⁵ and ocean climatology of ref.⁷⁶.

310 The three core simulations, BASE, noARI and noBCARI, are performed for five years spanning
311 the first two decades of the 21st century: 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, each with two months of
312 spin-up. BASE is the reference simulation while in noARI, aerosol-radiation interactions are switched
313 off by setting aer_ra_feedback=0 in the namelist. In noBCARI, aerosol-radiation interactions for BC
314 are switched off by setting the mass of BC to zero in the file module_optical_averaging.F. Similarly,
315 in simulations for year 2015 (+two months of spin-up) only, aerosol-radiation interactions have been
316 switched off for organic aerosols (noOAARI), sulphate (noSO4ARI), nitrate (noNO3ARI), ammonium
317 (noNH4ARI), sea salt (noSSARI), and dust (noDUSTARI). When showing map plots of differences
318 between simulations (in Figures 2 and 5), stippling indicates where at least 4 of the 5 simulation
319 years agree on the sign of change. However, a stricter requirement of all 5 years agreeing on the sign
320 of change does not substantially change the area of stippling in the plots (not shown).

323 **Health impact calculations**

324 In combination with the modelled data on ambient PM_{2.5} exposure and sensitivity ARI experiments,
325 we apply the MR-BRT (meta-regression-Bayesian, regularized, trimmed) exposure-response
326 function^{77,78}, which was also used in our previous studies^{1,79} and the most recent iteration of the
327 Global Burden of Disease study⁸⁰. Using the cause-specific exposure-response function, we estimate
328 excess deaths from ischemic heart disease (IHD), stroke (both ischemic and hemorrhagic), chronic
329 obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), lung cancer (LC), and Type II diabetes (T2DM) among adults
330 (aged 25 and above), as well as acute lower respiratory tract infections (ALRI) among children (under

331 5 years old). The excess death burden was calculated at a 5 × 5 km spatial resolution by interpolating
 332 the modeled exposure data, and the estimates were stratified by age and disease category, following
 333 the approach of our previous studies:

$$334 \quad M_{c,a,d} = BM_{a,d} \times P_a \times \frac{RR_{c,a,d} - 1}{RR_{c,a,d}} \quad (1)$$

335
 336 Excess deaths were estimated separately for adults and children at each 5 year intervals. RR(c,a,d)
 337 were derived using MR-BRT functions for all diseases by age, where c,a,d denotes concentration of
 338 PM_{2.5}, population age and disease respectively. Age specific RRs (Relative Risks) for IHD and stroke,
 339 are obtained using MR-BRT. For LC, T2DM, and COPD uniform RR(c,d) were used across all age
 340 groups among adults. BM(a,d) is the baseline mortality rate per 100,000 population, obtained from
 341 the GBD (<http://ghdx.healthdata.org/gbd-results-tool>) for India and China for respective years. We
 342 considered BM to remain uniform within a country at 5 × 5 km resolution by age and disease. P(a) is
 343 the exposed population in a grid by age; the age distributions at 5-year intervals (adults > 25 years),
 344 and <5 years for children were obtained from the GBD which are then merged with the gridded
 345 population data at about 5 × 5 km horizontal resolution from Global Human Settlement Layer
 346 (<https://human-settlement.emergency.copernicus.eu/>) to obtain the age-specific population (P(a))
 347 at each 5 × 5 km grid.

348

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 356 bio_emiss provided by the Atmospheric Chemistry Observations and Modeling Lab (ACOM) of NCAR.
 357

358 Data availability

359 The WHO Ambient Air quality database was downloaded from
 360 <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/air-pollution/who-air-quality-database>. MODIS data
 361 were obtained from the Giovanni online data system⁸¹, developed and maintained by the NASA
 362 Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center, while MISR data were obtained from
 363 the NASA Langley Research Center Atmospheric Science Data Center⁸². CRU TS data were obtained
 364 from <https://crudata.uea.ac.uk/cru/data/hrg/>. WRF-Chem model data will be made available on the
 365 NIRD research data archive, <https://archive.sigma2.no/>, upon publication.
 366

367 Author contributions

368 ØH carried out model simulations and LM helped with the model setup. KA and SC did health impact
 369 calculations. SW provided air pollution measurements. ØH, GM and CWS designed the study. ØH
 370 made the figures and wrote the manuscript with input from all authors.
 371

372 **Competing interests**

373 The authors declare no competing interests.

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593 Figure captions

594 **Figure 1. Evaluation of AOD and PM_{2.5}.** Annual mean AOD from WRF-Chem (a) and MODIS-Aqua (b), monthly mean AOD
 595 density scatter plot between MODIS-Aqua and WRF-Chem (c), annual mean PM_{2.5} from WRF-Chem and air quality
 596 monitoring stations (d-e), and probability density function of hourly PM_{2.5} for all stations shown in d (f). The WHO dataset
 597 in e includes stations that are outside of China but within the model domain (see Supplementary Figure 2).
 598

599 **Figure 2. Regional distributions of PM_{2.5} and turbulence.** 5-year averages of near-surface total PM_{2.5} and BC-only PM_{2.5} in
 600 BASE (a,e), and relative changes in near-surface turbulent kinetic energy (b,f), PBL height (c,g), and near-surface total PM_{2.5}
 601 (d,h) due to ARI from all aerosols (BASE-noARI) and due to ARI from BC-only (BASE-noBCARI). Stippling indicates where at
 602 least 4 of the 5 years agree on the sign of change.
 603

604 **Figure 3. Regionally averaged vertical profiles.** Mass mixing ratios of PM_{2.5} aerosol compounds in BASE (a,i) and changes in
 605 meteorological variables (b-g and j-o) and total PM_{2.5} (h,p) due to ARI from black carbon only (BCARI: BASE-noBCARI),
 606 organic aerosols only (OAARI: BASE-noOAARI), sulphate only (SO4ARI: BASE-noSO4ARI), nitrate only (NO3ARI: BASE-
 607 noNO3ARI), ammonium only (NH4ARI: BASE-noNH4ARI), sea salt only (SSARI: BASE-noSSARI), dust only (DUSTARI: BASE-
 608 noDUSTARI), and all aerosols (ARI: BASE-noARI) for year 2015 over the two regions indicated by the black rectangles in
 609 Figure 2a. Variable “W” is vertical velocity. Shadings for BCARI and ARI represent the range of all 5 simulated years.
 610

611 **Figure 4. Regionally averaged seasonal cycle.** PM_{2.5} aerosol compounds in BASE (a,b) and changes in meteorological
 612 variables (c-j) and total PM_{2.5} (k,l) due to ARI from black carbon only (BCARI: BASE-noBCARI), organic aerosols only (OAARI:
 613 BASE-noOAARI), sulphate only (SO4ARI: BASE-noSO4ARI), nitrate only (NO3ARI: BASE-noNO3ARI), ammonium only
 614 (NH4ARI: BASE-noNH4ARI), sea salt only (SSARI: BASE-noSSARI), dust only (DUSTARI: BASE-noDUSTARI), and all aerosols
 615 (ARI: BASE-noARI) for year 2015 over the two regions indicated by the black rectangles in Figure 2a. Bars show annual
 616 means. Shadings for BCARI and ARI represent the range of all 5 simulated years.
 617

618 **Figure 5. Regional distributions of health-related metrics.** 5-year average of change in excess deaths due to long-term
 619 exposure of PM_{2.5} (a,e), change in the number of haze days (PM_{2.5} > 75 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) (b,f), relative change in annual-mean ozone
 620 (c,g), and change in days with maximum hourly heat index exceeding 41°C (d,h) due to ARI from all aerosols (BASE-noARI;
 621 top) and ARI from BC-only (BASE-noBCARI; bottom). Stippling indicates where at least 4 of the 5 years agree on the sign of
 622 change.
 623